

Changing Landscape in Tobacco Cessation

Mini Thomas, MSN, RN; Asma Taha RN, PhD, CPNP, PCNS-BC; and Cindy Greenberg, DNSc, RN, PNP-BC, FAAN

Background

- Smoking is the foremost preventable cause for morbidity and mortality
- 40 million Americans are smokers
- Multiple types of tobacco products are emerging, including e-cigarettes and hookah
- Tobacco in any form is harmful
- Higher prevalence of tobacco use among people with chronic disease conditions
- Newer tobacco products are a threat to the current decline in tobacco use
- Nurses can play a key role in screening, counseling, and initiating pharmacotherapy and other cessation strategies
- Tobacco cessation education can increase nurse's confidence and participation

Significance

- Quitting can reduce tobacco's potential harm by 90%
- Hospital setting is a key environment for initiating tobacco cessation

Purpose

Develop a tobacco cessation education program for staff nurses in an acute care facility.

Tobacco Cessation Education Module

Theoretical Framework: Iowa Model

Denotes Decision Making Point
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Tobacco in Any Form is Harmful

Implications for Practice

- Tobacco cessation education can improve the nurse's confidence in implementing tobacco cessation interventions
- Participation in tobacco cessation will increase the compliance with accreditation agencies
- Tobacco cessation can help in reducing the morbidity and mortality as well as health expenditure

Recommendations

- Offer tobacco cessation education for nurses every two years
- Audit tobacco cessation intervention in the hospital for identifying gaps in practice
- Revise tobacco cessation education as needed per evidence based practice